

APECS Annual Report 2015-2016

1 October 2015 – 30 September 2016

Executive Summary

Welcome to the APECS annual report for 2015-2016. Inside you will find a wealth of information about what we have been doing the last year, from workshops to webinars.

One of the key tasks for APECS this year was to develop a five-year strategic plan based on the recommendations provided by the organizational review committee. The APECS Strategic Plan for 2016-2020 outlines key areas for APECS to concentrate on in order to continue developing as an organization. Already this year, we made a number of changes. For example, we created two National Committee coordinator positions within the APECS Council to act as a link between our growing number of National Committees and the APECS Leadership, developed our social media presence, and re-organized council tasks into clearly defined projects (e.g. Antarctica Day project group).

A highlight of the year was the launch of the APECS Mentorship Award. The inaugural award was presented to Dave Carlson (Director of the World Climate Research Programme) at the Arctic Science Summit Week in Fairbanks, Alaska in March. Without Dave's unfailing support and encouragement to APECS members (and numerous other early career researchers), it is safe to say that APECS would not be where it is today.

Our transition to a new membership database is now complete and we already have over 2000 members signed up from 62 different countries and territories. Our National Committees do a tremendous amount of outreach and organize many events, especially around the International Polar Weeks and Antarctica Day. This year we are delighted that two new National Committees were established and one re-established. APECS Germany will now provide a long-awaited national committee for the 7% of our members who reside there, APECS Chile will help us strengthen our presence in South America and the southern hemisphere, and we welcome back APECS Belgium!

We are continuing to create opportunities for our members to gain scientific committee and policy experience and, thanks to the great feedback from groups with existing representatives, we are receiving more and more requests from organizations looking for APECS members to serve on their committees. For example, this year, we were able to appoint a number of representatives to SCAR working groups.

All of what you read in this report would not have been possible without our dedicated members who put in the extra voluntary hours to make things happen. I wish to thank all of our members and mentors for their time and enthusiasm over the past year, our partners and sponsors for their continuous support and of course to our Directorate sponsors (the Research Council of Norway, UiT The Arctic University of Norway and the Norwegian Polar Institute).

I hope you will be inspired by reading this report and that you will join us for what is shaping up to be a very exciting year ahead!

Ruth Vingerhagen
APECS President 2015-2016

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Chapter 1: Organizational Overview

1.1. APECS Leadership

The APECS leadership is comprised of early career researchers that are interested in and committed to furthering the activities and the future directions of the organisation. An Executive Committee and Council lead the organisation supported by the international Directorate.

APECS Executive Committee 2015 - 2016	
APECS President	Dr. Ruth Vingerhagen - University of Cambridge - United Kingdom
APECS Vice-Presidents	Alice Bradley - University of Colorado Boulder - United States Dr. Heather Mariash - National Wildlife Research Centre - Canada Hanne Nielsen - University of Tasmania - Australia Dr. Trista Vick-Majors - Montana State University - United States
ex-officios	Dr. Jean-Sébastien Moore - Université Laval - Canada Yulia Zaika - M.V. Lomonosov Moscow State University - Russia
Temporary Member*	Sara Strey - University of Illinois at Urbana Champaign - United States

* filling in for Executive Committee Members during extended absences

APECS Council 2015 - 2016

Council Chairs	<p>Rachel Downey - Naturmuseum Senckenberg - Germany / Australia</p> <p>Scott Zolkos - University of Alberta - Canada</p>
National Committee Coordinators	<p>Dr. Mar Fernandez Mendez - Norwegian Polar Institute - Norway</p> <p>Alex Thornton - University of Alaska Fairbanks - United States</p>
Council Members	<p>Adam Campbell - University of Otago - New Zealand</p> <p>Jennifer Cooper - CSULA - United States</p> <p>Kristina Creek - ARCUS - United States</p> <p>Archana Dayal - National Centre for Antarctic and Ocean Research - India</p> <p>Alena Dekhtyareva - UiT The Arctic University of Norway - Norway</p> <p>Dr. Ivan Dubinenkov - Alfred Wegener Institute - Germany / Russia</p> <p>Friederike Gehrmann - University of Helsinki - Finland</p> <p>Vikram Goel - Norwegian Polar Institute - Norway</p> <p>Meagan Grabowski - University of British Columbia - Canada</p> <p>Gunnar Mar Gunnarsson - Scott Polar Research Institute - United Kingdom</p> <p>Svenja Halfter - University of Rostock - Germany</p> <p>Lara Hugues-Allen - University of Southern California - United States</p> <p>Ming Jing - China Meteorological Administration - China</p> <p>Alia Khan - University of Colorado - Boulder - United States</p> <p>Nikita Kuprikov - Russian Polar Initiative - Russia</p> <p>Dr. Elena Kuznetsova - Norwegian University of Science and Technology - Norway</p> <p>Beatrice Laudet - France</p> <p>Lydie Lescarmontier - France</p> <p>Juliana Marson - University of Alberta - Canada</p> <p>Claudia Maturana - Universidad de Chile - Chile</p> <p>Ellorie McKnight - University of Alberta - Canada</p> <p>Bernabé Moreno - Científica del Sur University - Peru</p> <p>Karolina Paquin - Norway</p> <p>Vicki Sahanatien - Canada</p> <p>Sara Strey - University of Illinois at Urbana Champaign - United States</p> <p>Camila Signori - University of Sao Paulo - Brazil</p> <p>Paul Suprenand - Mote Marine Laboratory - United States</p> <p>Zuzanna Swirad - Durham University - United Kingdom</p> <p>Lorna Thurston - Northern Arizona University - United States</p> <p>Ekaterina Uryupova - University of Salford - United Kingdom</p> <p>Anna Varfolomeeva - Central European University - Hungary</p> <p>Matthias Wietz - University of Oldenburg - Germany</p>
ex-officio	<p>Dr. Allen Pope - National Snow and Ice Data Center - United States</p> <p>Dr. Mariette Wheeler - Department of Environmental Affairs, Ocean and Coasts/Bird's-Eye View Productions - South Africa</p>

APECS International Directorate

The main APECS International Directorate and Executive Director are funded by the generous support of the [Research Council of Norway](#), [UiT The Arctic University of Norway](#) and the [Norwegian Polar Institute](#). The office is housed at UiT at the Faculty of Biosciences, Fisheries and Economics in Tromsø, Norway. The APECS Executive Director is the essential coordinator, whose work makes the running of the organization and various APECS activities and programmes possible. APECS is especially grateful for the continued support provided by its Directorate sponsors.

In addition, Murmansk Arctic State University, funds a part-time APECS Officer for the APECS International Directorate located in Murmansk, Russia from July 2016 to February 2017. APECS is very grateful for this additional staff support.

APECS International Directorate

Executive Director*

Dr. Gerlis Fugmann - Association of Polar Early Career Scientists / UiT The Arctic University of Norway - Norway

APECS Officer**

Yulia Sultanbayeva - Murmansk Arctic State University - Russia

* funded full-time through Research Council of Norway, UiT The Arctic University of Norway, Norwegian Polar Institute, Norway

** funded part-time through Murmansk Arctic State University, Russia since July 2016

1.2. APECS National Committees

To better respond to the needs of specific countries, APECS has National Committees (NCs), which are linked to, and comprise a vital part of, the international APECS network. Some countries have well established NCs, whereas others are just getting started. APECS currently has 23 active NC's working at the national level with locally based early career researchers. In addition, a number of other countries keep active mailing lists or social media profiles but are not formal committees at the moment. Find out more about the [APECS National Committees and how to contact them on the APECS website](#).

Map 1: APECS National Committees 2015-2016

APECS National Committee Leaderships 2015-2016

APECS Belgium

Henrik Christiansen (KU Leuven); *Igor Stelmach Pessi* (Université de Liège)

APECS Brazil

(Associação de Pesquisadores educadores em Início de Carreira sobre o Mar e os Polos)

Dra Juliana Assunção Ivar do Sul (President); *Biol. Juliana Silva Souza* (Vice-President), *Adriana R. de Lira Pessoa* (1a Secretary), *Ana Olivia de A. Reis* (2a Secretary), *Luiz Antonio da Costa* (Secretary Support), *Claudineia Lizieri* (1a Treasurer), *Douglas Lindemann* (2o Treasurer), *Fernanda Quaglio* (1a Scientific Coordinator), *Adriano Lemos* (2o Scientific Coordinator), *Rodrigo Alves* (Scientific Support), *Sandra Freiberger Affonso* (1o Education and Outreach Coordinator), *Roberta Piuco* (2o Education and Outreach Coordinator), *Alessandra Zanin* (Education and Outreach Support), *Erli Schneider Costa* (UERGS) (1a Projects Developer Coordinator), *Gerusa Radichi* (2a Projects Developer Coordinator), *Hugo Mariz* (Projects Developer Support), *Silvia Dotta* (1o Graduation Action Coordinator), *Claudineia Lizieri* (2a Graduation Action Coordinator), *Ailim Schwambach* (Graduation

Support), **Thiago Severo** (10 Resources Coordinator), **Sueli Matos** (20 Resources Coordinator)

APECS Bulgaria	Iglika Trifonova (Sofia University), Denitsa Apostolova (Sofia University), Asparuh Kamburov (University of Mining and Geology "St. Ivan Rilski")
APECS Chile	Sebastian Ruiz (Universidad de Magallanes); Joaquin Bastias (Universidad de Chile); Claudia Maturana (Universidad de Chile)
APECS Canada	Ann Balasubramaniam (Communications Coordinator); Kristina Brown ; Louise Chavarie ; Marianne Falardeau-Cote ; Meagan Grabowski (Co-Vice Chair International Relations); Lawrence Hislop ; Adam Houben (Vice-Chair Administration); Gabriela Ibarguchi ; Marney Paradis ; Kristen Peck (Education and Outreach Co-Coordinator); Daniel Pomerants ; Jennifer Provencher (Co-Vice Chair International Relations); Pacale Ropars ; Vicki Sahanatien (Chair APECS Canada); Laura Thomson (Education and Outreach Co-Coordinator); Melissa Ward ; Nikolaus Gantner (ex-officio).
APECS Finland	Friederike Gehrmann (University of Helsinki)
APECS France	Céline Clément-Chastel (president), Lydie Lescarmontier (vice-president), Gaëlle Lamarque (vice-president) (Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Norte, Brazil), Veronique Dansereau (treasurer) (Laboratoire de Glaciologie et Géophysique de l'Environnement), Sophie Schiavone (secretary) (Laboratoire ThéMA / University Franche-Comté)
APECS Germany	Josefine Lenz (Alfred Wegener Institute); Andreas Preußner (University of Trier / ILTS Sapporo); Caroline Coch (Alfred Wegener Institute); Heike Link (University of Kiel); Stefanie Weege (Alfred Wegener Institute); Liv Heinecke (Alfred Wegener Institute); Christian Katlein (Alfred Wegener Institute); Stefanie Arndt (Alfred Wegener Institute); Clara Burgard (MPI Hamburg); Muhammed Arsalan Afzal (University of Köln); Matteo Puglini (MPI Hamburg); Svenja Kohnemann (University of Trier); Johanna Grabow (University of Leipzig); Svenja Halfter ; Kathrin Keil (IASS); Rita Melo Franco Santos (Alfred Wegener Institute); Magnus Schneider (University of Trier); Charlotte Havermans (Alfred Wegener Institute / University Bremen); Alevtina Evgrafova (University Koblenz-Landau / University Bern)
Indian Polar Research Network	Anant Pande (Wildlife Institute of India); Archana Dayal (University of Sheffield, UK)
APECS Italy	Andrea Spolaor , Giuseppe Aulicino , Matteo Cattadori , Tosca Ballerini
APECS Japan	October 2015 - March 2016 : Shunsuke Tei (National Institute of Polar Research), Kazuki Nakata (Hokkaido University), Ryo Shingubara (Hokkaido University), Shinya Takano (Hokkaido University), Tomoki Morozumi (Hokkaido University); April 2016 - March 2017 : Shunsuke Tei (Hokkaido University), Shun Tsutaki (Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency), Daiki Sakakibara (Hokkaido University), Naoya Kanna (Hokkaido University), Kazuki Nakata (Hokkaido University).
APECS Malaysia	Leela Salwoom ; Wan Lutfi Bin Wan Johari , Ming Li Teoh , Abiramy Krishnan , Nor Farah Natasha Tajuddin , Shoba Thomas , Nuradilla Mohammad Fauzi , Wee Cheah , Nur Aqilah Muhamad Darif Lim Wei Ming , Yeoh Chiann Ying , Sheeba Chenoli , Anna Komar , Nur Adeela Yasid , Siti Aqlima Ahmad , Wong Chiew Yen , Emineour Muzalina , Malcolm Tang , Muhamad Hilal Mohd Zainudin , Chan Kok Keong , Azra Firzadh Asangany
APECS Netherlands	Douwe Maat (Netherlands Institute for Sea Research), Ariadna Szczybelski (Wageningen University)

APECS Oceania (Australia and New Zealand)	Hanne Nielsen (University of Tasmania, Australia), Gabriela Roldan (University of Canterbury, New Zealand), Indi Hodgson-Johnston (University of Tasmania, Australia), Meagan Dewar (Deakin University, Australia), Julie Janssens (University of Tasmania, Australia), Mana Inoue (University of Tasmania, Australia), Harriet Love (Otago University, New Zealand), Eleri Evans (University of Tasmania, Australia). The following members stepped aside during this term: Sira Engelbertz (New Zealand), Lorna Little (New Zealand), Holly Winton (Australia)
APECS Peru	Bernabé Moreno (Científica del Sur University, Peru); Bruno Ibañez (Universidad Peruana Cayetano Heredia)
APECS Poland	Maja Lisowska (University of Silesia); Marta Bystrowska (University of Silesia)
APECS Portugal	Sara Aparicio - European Space Agency; Filipa Carvalho - Rutgers University; José Seco - University of St. Andrews / University of Coimbra; José Queirós - MARE Marine and Environmental Sciences Centre.
Russian Polar Initiative	Ivan Dubinenkov - NGO Polar Initiative, Nikita Kuprikov - Moscow Aviation Institute / NGO Polar Initiative, Denis Doronin - Arctic Antarctic Research Institute
APECS Sweden	Patrícia Pečnerová (Executive Secretary) (Stockholm University); Ylva Sjöberg (Stockholm University); Eric Paglia (KTH); Céline Heuzé (University of Gothenburg); Mats Björkman (University of Gothenburg); Matthias Siewert (Stockholm University); Juri Palmtag (Stockholm University); Christopher Cosgrove (Uppsala University); Magdalena Pfaffl (James Cook University).
APECS Switzerland	Saskia Gindraux - Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research WSL; Martin Proksch - WSL-Institute for Snow and Avalanche Research SLF.
APECS Turkey	Burcu Ozsoy - ITU Polar Research Center (ITU PolReC), Ozgun Oktar - ITU Polar Research Center (ITU PolReC)
UK Polar Network	TJ Young (University of Cambridge & British Antarctic Survey); Sammie Buzzard (University of Reading); Laura Hobbs (Scottish Association of Marine Sciences); Gunnar Mallon (University of Sheffield); Archana Dayal (University of Sheffield); Kyle Mayers (National Oceanography Centre); Catherine Docherty (University of Birmingham); Jenny Turton (British Antarctic Survey & University of Leeds); Madeleine Brasier (University of Liverpool & the National Oceanographic Centre); Michelle McCrystall (British Antarctic Survey & University of Cambridge); Dwayne Menezes (Human Security Centre); Kassandra Reuss-Schmidt (University of Sheffield); Ruth Vingerhagen (University of St. Andrews); Amber Leeson (University of Lancaster); Scott Davidson (University of Sheffield); Lucy Hyam (Scottish Association of Marine Sciences); Eleanor Darlington (Loughborough University); Jon Hawkings (University of Bristol); Eleanor Jones (University of Sheffield); Julia Feuer-Cotter (University of Nottingham).
US APECS (United States)	Ellyn Enderlin (Co-Chair) (University of Maine); Alex Thornton (Co-Chair) (University of Alaska Fairbanks); Alice Bradley (University of Colorado); Allen Pope (University of Colorado); Lauren Frisch (University of Alaska Fairbanks); Mia Bennett (University of California Los Angeles); Olivia Lee (University of Alaska Fairbanks); Sophia Albov (University of Helsinki); Ariel Morrison (University of Colorado); Jim Crowell (Arizona State University).

1.3. APECS Membership 2015-2016

Since the creation of APECS, well over 5500 people from more than 75 countries have registered as APECS members on the APECS website or through one of the many APECS National Committees during the early stages of their scientific careers. APECS also currently has 3203 “likes” on the APECS Facebook page as well as 2827 members in the APECS Facebook Group and 4576 followers on Twitter (@Polar_Research) plus those associated with the various Social Media presences of the APECS National Committees¹.

In July 2015, APECS started a large update of its member database associated with a switch to a new mailing list. This process is now complete and below are a number of interesting facts about membership of 2131 active members¹. The top 5 countries of 64 total in membership numbers in APECS representing 53.5% of the APECS membership are: 1) United States, 2) Canada, 3) United Kingdom, 4) Germany, and 5) Brazil.

Map 2: Countries with active APECS members (blue) and National Committees (orange) (data as of 3 October 2016).

The gender information shows that 59% of APECS members are female and 40% male. Master and Doctoral Students as well as Postdoctoral Researchers represent a combined 69% of the APECS members. The career level of the remaining 31% includes undergraduate students, research scientists, faculty members, teachers and others.

¹ All numbers in this chapter as 3 October 2016

The member registration form also allows members to provide information on the regional focus of their research as well as the research disciplines they represent, with the ability to select multiple answers. Figure 1 shows the research disciplines and percentage of members that selected them.

Figure 1: A distribution of disciplines is shown above, with environmental science, ecology and geosciences being the most popular fields of members.

APECS traditionally represents members that are conducting research in the Polar Regions, which also shows in the regional focus selections made: 50% stated they are involved in Antarctic research and 72% are involved in Arctic research. It should be noted that 17% of the members selected both Arctic and Antarctic. Also, 21% are involved in Alpine research, and about 10% each in research in the Himalaya and other regions of the world. Multiple answers were possible for this question.

Chapter 2: Helping Members Interact

One of the goals of APECS International is to create opportunities for the development of innovative, international, and interdisciplinary collaborations among early career polar researchers. Specifically we aim to:

- Create a network of polar researchers across disciplines and national boundaries to meet, share ideas and experiences, and develop new research directions and collaborations
- Provide the opportunity for career development for both traditional and alternative polar and cryosphere professions

2.1. APECS events for early career researchers

APECS and its National Committees organize events (e.g. workshops, panel discussions, networking events) regularly around the world. Map 3 and table 2.1. show the APECS events for early career researchers held around the world in 2015-2016. A summary for most of the events can be found on the APECS website through the link provided in the table. We highlight a few of the events below the table. Since the APECS International Directorate office is located in Norway, we also highlight some of the Norwegian events.

Map 3: APECS events for early career researchers in 2015-2016

Table 2.1: APECS events for early career researchers

No.*	Title	Date	Place
Events (co)organized with APECS International			
1	Data Management Workshop at Polar Data Forum II <i>Organizers:</i> APECS, ArcticNet Students' Association , with additional support from the University of Waterloo.	27 Oct 2015	Waterloo, Canada
2	APECS-AGU Cryosphere Careers Panel and Pub Meetup	16 Dec 2015	San Francisco, USA
3	Science Communication Panel at Arctic Frontiers 2016 <i>Organizer:</i> APECS, <i>High North Academy (HNA)</i>	27 Jan 2015	Tromsø, Norway
4	Arctic Frontiers Early Career Poster Awards 2016 <i>Organizers:</i> APECS, Arctic Frontiers	28 Jan 2015	Tromsø, Norway
5	APECS Executive Committee in-person meeting	10-11 Mar 2016	Fairbanks, USA
6	APECS Early Career Arctic Policy Workshop at the ASSW 2016	14 Mar 2016	Fairbanks, USA
7	Young Researcher Workshop at ICOP 2016 <i>Organizers:</i> PYRN, APECS, young researcher representatives of the USPA, and ADAPT.	18-19 Jun 2016	Potsdam, Germany
8	APECS Career Development Workshop at SCAR OSC 2016	21 Aug 2016	Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia
9	Early Career Presentation Awards at SCAR OSC 2016	26 Aug 2016	Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia
Events (co)organized by APECS National Committees			
10	ECR Panel Academics, Research and Jobs in the North: Perspectives from Early-Career Scientists <i>Organizer:</i> APECS Canada and Skookum Jim Friendship Centre	22 Sept 2015	Whitehorse, Canada
11	VI Workshop of Career Development of APECS Portugal <i>Organizer:</i> APECS Portugal	28 Oct 2015	Évora, Portugal
12	APECS Netherlands Symposium 2015 <i>Organizer:</i> APECS Netherlands	6 Nov 2015	Den Haag, Netherlands
13	Social at Arctic Observing Open Science Meeting (AOOSM) <i>Organizer:</i> USAPECS	18 Nov 2015	Seattle, USA
14	Forum and Roundtable on Young Scientists at the Arctic Days 2015 Conference <i>Co-Organizer:</i> Russian Polar Initiative	20 Nov 2015	Moscow, Russia

15	Early career panel and official public APECS Switzerland kick-off at Swiss Geoscience Meeting Organizer: APECS Switzerland	21 Nov 2015	Basel, Switzerland
16	Panel at the Forum "The Arctic: Present and Future" Co-Organizer: Russian Polar Initiative	7 Dec 2015	St. Petersburg, Russia
17	ArcticNet Student Day by ASA-APECS Organizers: ArcticNet Student Association (ASA) and APECS Canada	7-8 Dec 2015	Vancouver, Canada
18	Geodesy and travels Workshop at in the University of Architecture, Civil Engineering and Geodesy (UACEG) Organizer: APECS Bulgaria	April 2015	Sofia, Bulgaria
19	APECS JAPAN meeting at Japan Geoscience Union meeting 2016 Organizer: APECS Japan	26 May 2016	Chiba, Japan
20	APECS Poland workshop for young researchers dedicated to interdisciplinary cooperation in polar science Organizer: APECS Poland, Faculty of Earth Sciences and Spatial Management, University of Maria Curie-Skłodowska	8 June 2016	Lublin, Poland
21	Excursion to the high-alpine research station Jungfrauoch Organizer: APECS Switzerland	17 June 2016	Jungfrauoch, Switzerland
22	Workshop at UK Antarctic Science Conference Organizer: UK Polar Network	4-5 July 2016	Norwich, UK
23	International Glaciological Society (IGS) Research-Life Balance Panel Organizer: USAPECS	12 July 2016	La Jolla, USA
24	IV APECS-Brazil Symposium: Legacy and Perspectives of the Madrid Protocol: 25-years of history and the next 25-years Organizer: APECS Brazil	27-29 July 2016	Brasília Brazil
25	"APECS Belgium – Get to Know Meeting" Organizer: APECS Belgium	17 Aug. 2016	Brussels, Belgium
26	Panel discussion "What makes a successful proposal" at coordination workshop by the German Research Foundation's Priority Program on Antarctic Research Organizer: APECS Germany	14 Sept. 2016	Rostock, Germany
27	APECS Social nights in Whitehorse, Yukon Organizer: APECS Canada	Every few months	Whitehorse, Canada
28	APECS France Seminars at laboratories and research facilities across France	Several	France

*Indicates Number in Map 3

International Highlights:

Early Career Arctic Policy Workshop at ASSW 2016

14 March 2016

Fairbanks, Alaska, United States

APECS hosted an Early Career Arctic Policy Workshop on Monday, March 14 during Arctic Science Summit Week in Fairbanks, Alaska. This half-day workshop began with a keynote presentation from Bradley Moran, dean of the University of Alaska Fairbanks School of Fisheries and Ocean Sciences. Following, participants heard five short presentations addressing the global effort to use best-available science in the development of Arctic policy from our workshop's mentors: Carolina Behe, Terry Chapin, Henry Huntington, Amy Lovecraft, and Peter Winsor. Following the talks, participants broke into smaller, mentor-led groups to discuss strategies for incorporating scientific knowledge into impactful Arctic policy. The workshop had great attendance, with 34 participants from a range of countries and different career stages.

APECS Career Development Workshop at the SCAR Open Science Conference 2016

21 August 2016

Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia

A full day APECS workshop was held in Malaysia on August 21, immediately prior to the 2016 SCAR Open Science Conference. This workshop attracted over 60 participants, with early career researchers

from all over the globe attending. Jose Xavier from the British Antarctic Survey opened the workshop, presenting on “Networking Skills: an important soft skill for a scientist?” Next, Renuka Badhe from the European Polar Board provided an introduction to “International Cooperation and Interdisciplinary Work.” The second part of the morning was spent learning about some of the unique projects and products that were being launched or further developed at SCAR 2016. For many of those present, the workshop was their first APECS event. APECS Director Gerlis Fugmann presented an introduction to “The Association of Polar Early Career Scientists and How to Get Involved” in order to outline the many activities APECS is involved in. Hanne Nielsen, from APECS Oceania, and Alex Thornton, from USAPECS, then talked about their National Committee activities. Lunch was followed by a plenary discussion on Career Paths. The final session of the day involved two breakout sessions, one on “Writing Funding Applications,” and the other on “Sharpening Communication Skills.” Many thanks to all of the mentors who helped to make the workshop a success, to Antarctic Science for providing lunch, and to the SCAR 2016 conference for providing a venue and coffee breaks. The workshop was organised by Hanne Nielsen, Alex Thornton, Bernabé Moreno, Jennifer Cooper, and Gerlis Fugmann.

Norwegian Highlights:

Science Communication Panel at Arctic Frontiers 2016

27 January 2016

Tromsø, Norway

On Wednesday 27 January 2016, **APECS**, in cooperation with the **High North Academy (HNA)**, arranged a panel discussion dedicated to science communication during the Arctic Frontiers conference at the UiT The Arctic University of Norway. The four speakers (Lawrence Hislop, CliC; Magnus Svendsen Nerheim, University of Bergen; Alexey Pavlov, Norwegian Polar Institute; Sara Aparício, APECS Portugal) – all science communication advocates, shared their experiences and insights on communicating science from a broad and wide range of perspectives. The session was followed with a very exciting discussion between the panel and the public regarding experiences in communicating science and new tools. One of the main topics focussed on the challenges faced by scientists on keeping up with their work and feeding the always-hungry social media along the way. A very tricky balance of time consumption and work productivity!

Arctic Frontiers Poster Awards 2016

28 January 2016

Tromsø, Norway

The poster session for the Arctic Frontiers conference was held on Thursday afternoon. Posters were divided into three different themes: Arctic Stewardship, Environmental Footprints and Technology Needs. The poster hall was filled with lively discussions but some posters were getting more detailed attention and these were the 40 posters being presented by early career scientists. A team of judges evaluated the posters and then had a long discussion in order to decide the winners. It was not an easy decision due to the high quality of all the posters but in the end we decided on an overall winner and three runner-ups. The awards were presented at the Science Conference dinner at the Scandic Ishavshotel.

2.2 Education and Outreach Events

Education and Outreach is one of the main focus areas of APECS. During 2015-2016, APECS and its National Committees again organized many events dedicated to the public around the world. In addition, APECS organized two International Polar Weeks in September 2015 and March 2016 as well as participated with several partners in Antarctica Day, providing an opportunity for focused education and outreach activities around the world during these times:

Map 3: APECS Education and Outreach Events during 2015-2016

Table 2.2.: Worldwide outreach events for the International Polar Weeks Fall 2015, Spring 2016 and Fall 2016

No.*	Title / Link	Location
International Polar Week Fall 2015 19 - 26 September 2015 Below events reported by APECS and its National Committees. A full list of events is on the Polar Week page .		
1	#TweetYourThesis during Polar Week	Online / Twitter
2	Portuguese Polar Week (4 - 10 October 2015) Organizer: APECS Portugal	Portugal
3	Polar Week celebration Organizer: Indian Polar Research Network	India

4	US APECS / UKPN Polar Week Reddit Science AMA ("Ask Me Anything") (20 September 2015)	Online
5	APECS Francophone Polar Week (21 - 27 September 2015) <i>Organizer:</i> APECS Canada and APECS France	Online
Antarctica Day 2015 1 December 2015 Many events were organized worldwide. For a full list, go see the Antarctica Day 2015 Event List . Below are some highlights of activities reported specifically from APECS National Committees:		
6	Antarctica Day School Visits to various schools in Bulgaria <i>Organizer:</i> APECS Bulgaria	Bulgaria
7	Antarctica Day Celebration "Polar Week at Bulgaria Mall" including photo exhibition <i>Organizer:</i> APECS Bulgaria	Sofia, Bulgaria
8	"Antarctica Flags" event with 22 participating schools and 150 flags produced (taken to Antarctica by 16 deliverers) <i>Organizer:</i> UK Polar Network	Worldwide
9	School talks and hands-on activities at several schools <i>Organizer:</i> APECS Spain	Barcelona, Spain
10	Presentation to 70 children from 6th grade about Antarctica through pictures and videos <i>Organizer:</i> APECS Spain and National Museum of Natural Science.	Madrid, Spain
11	Organization of a small cycle of four outreach conferences about science and conservation, lichens, fauna and contamination of the white continent <i>Organizer:</i> APECS Spain in collaboration with National Museum of Natural Science and the "Friends of the Museum"	Madrid, Spain
12	Book exhibition of books from the first Antarctic expeditions <i>Organizer:</i> APECS Spain in collaboration with National Museum of Natural Science	Madrid, Spain
13	POLAR EDUCATION Antarctica Day: APECS-France worked with SCAR at the booth of the International Cryosphere Climate Initiative (ICCI) at the Nordic Pavilion of COP21 to represent APECS, to communicate about Polar Research and Polar Research Outreach. <i>Organizers:</i> APECS France in cooperation with SCAR and ICCI	Paris, France
14	APECS-France Participating in the 11th Conference of Youth (COY11) including organizing / facilitating scientific talks, quizzes, and workshops to help people discover all the research led by young polar researchers and better understand the vital role of Polar Regions in the global climate system.	Paris, France
15	Roundtable Discussion with APECS France about Arctic research during 2-day event co-organized with Tara Expeditions	Paris, France
16	APECS (@Polar_Research) tweeted about #Antarctica around the clock, sharing stories about research, images, penguin gifs, and everything Antarctic.	Online

International Polar Week [Spring 2016](#)

14 – 20 March 2016

Below events reported by APECS and its National Committees. A full list of events is on the [Polar Week page](#).

17	APECS International Polar Week Fieldwork Photo Competition 2016 See all the winners here. Organizer: APECS	Online
18	International Polar Week in Brazil included approximately 1100 students and 25 teachers at 12 schools from different parts of Brazil (March-July 2016). Organizer: APECS Brazil	Brazil
19	Polar Week in Nunavut: One film night (Arctic research and traditional knowledge) and a poster session in with Nunavut Arctic College Organizer: APECS Canada	Iqaluit, Canada
20	Polar Week in Nunavut: APECS Canada (Vicki Sahanatien) developed and held a winter camp for Aboriginal youth. This included skiing, trekking and winter survival training (quinzhee building)!	Canada
21	APECS International Polar Week Webinars for Schools connecting ECRs to classrooms (6 webinars in total in French and English) Organizers: APECS Canada and APECS France	France, Canada
22	Polar Week film screening "Greenland is the melting point" Organizer: APECS Finland	Helsinki, Finland
23	Polar Day (Pool tot Pool) with APECS Netherlands	Leiden, Netherlands
24	APECS / BOTES Antarctic Quiz Night in Hobart at Institute for Marine and Antarctic Studies in collaboration with Bottom of the Earth Society (BOTES) Organizer: APECS Oceania	Hobart, Australia
25	Portuguese Polar Week coordinated by " Educação PROPOLAR "	Portugal
26	Film Screenings at Swedish Museum of Natural History and Stockholm University including follow up discussion and social event with posters and comics Organizer: APECS Sweden	Stockholm, Sweden
27	Leeds Science Festival outreach workshop, 'Pole to Pole: Life at the ends of the Earth', 21/03/16 Organizer: UK Polar Network	Leeds, UK
28	Curating @RealScientists Sammie Buzzard (UK Polar Network President) talking about polar related science all week. Organizer: UK Polar Network	Twitter, UK
29	Tweet Storm Tweet your polar thesis on @ehPECS #PolarWeek ! Organizer: APECS Canada	Twitter, Canada
30	Guest Bloggers on the Canadian science blog Science Borealis Organizer: APECS Canada	Canada
31	Flakes, Blobs, & Bubbles! (Polar Science Lesson with Activity) with APECS and PEI	Worldwide

32	School talks to celebrate International Polar Week Organizer: APECS Spain	Barcelona, Spain
33	1st National Challenge for creation of Apps (only in Portuguese) Organizer: APECS Brazil and State University of Rio Grande do Sul (UERGS)	Brazil
International Polar Week Fall 2016 19 - 26 September 2016 Below events reported by APECS and its National Committees. A full list of events is on the Polar Week page .		
34	APECS International Polar Week Figure Competition 2016 Polar week figure competition <i>See all the winners here.</i>	Online
35	Polar Film Festival <i>Organizer: US APECS</i>	Online
36	Movie night at Polar Week September 2016 <i>Organizer: APECS Germany</i>	Potsdam, Germany
37	Polar Film Festival participation <i>Organizer: UK Polar Network</i>	Cambridge, UK
38	Polar Film Fest: APECS Canada Watchparty in Whitehorse! <i>Organizer: APECS Canada</i>	Whitehorse, Canada
39	APECS Webinar: Understanding the ecological power of communication: Culture & nature tourism contexts <i>Organizer: APECS / APECS Oceania</i>	Online
40	APECS Oceania Social Media Presentation <i>Organizer: APECS Oceania</i>	Hobart, Australia and Online
41	Webinar Series for Schools <i>Organizer: APECS France</i>	Online
42	Poster session at the Australian Antarctic Week <i>Organizer: APECS Oceania</i>	Hobart, Australia
43	Celebration of polar week <i>Organizer: Indian Polar Research Network</i>	Dehradun, India
Other Education and Outreach Highlights		
44	Arctic Frontiers Science for Schools (26 - 28 January 2016) <i>Organizers: APECS, Nordnorsk Vitensenter, Arctic Frontiers</i>	Tromsø, Norway
45	Arctic Frontiers Science for Politics (27 January 2016) <i>Organizers: APECS, Nordnorsk Vitensenter, Arctic Frontiers</i>	Tromsø, Norway

*indicated number in Map 4

Norwegian Education and Outreach Highlights:

Arctic Frontiers Science for Schools 2016

26 - 28 January 2016

Tromsø, Norway

The Arctic Frontiers conference takes place every year in Tromsø, setting the perfect scene for polar outreach. During two days, 130 kids from the 10th grade class (13-14 years old) of four different local schools attended the Science for Schools event organized by UiT The Arctic University of Norway, Polaria, the Fram Centre, the Science Centre of Northern Norway and APECS. These kids live here, in the Arctic, in the main city of northern Norway, so they are familiar with snow and ice. However, most of them have never been out on a research vessel in the Arctic Ocean, on top of a glacier or diving below sea-ice. Therefore, listening to the first hand experiences of polar research scientists that have been there was extremely interesting for them.

Researchers from different nationalities living in Tromsø and abroad shared their experiences with the kids and were happy to answer all their curious questions. After the talks and hands-on experiences, it was the kids turn to impress us by presenting the posters, which they had been working on for the last month. In a way, it was their first mini-poster session at a scientific conference, and we have to say that the level of the posters was amazingly good. Not to mention their impressive level of English (not their native language). Some of us acted as judges, evaluating the posters and asking the kids questions about the topic they had chosen to present. Although it was a hard decision, we chose three second prizes and one overall winner. The winning poster (Lotion in the Arctic Ocean) could have perfectly been hanging at a regular scientific conference. There is definitely a lesson to be learned for all of us, researchers: We shouldn't lose our childish curiosity and our teenager excitement when presenting our work to others.

Arctic Frontiers Science for Politics

27 January 2016

Tromsø, Norway

The Arctic is changing rapidly due to human-induced global warming. While (us) researchers have known that for the last three decades, no significant progress has been made globally to prevent further warming of the climate in general and the Arctic, in particular. Partly, this is due to the lack of knowledge of decision makers and the public. Climate change misinformation is partially caused by a deficient information transfer from researchers to society, and especially to the younger generations who are still open-minded and eager to change the world. To improve the situation, this year, a special event for young politicians was organized by APECS during the Arctic Frontiers Conference in Tromsø, Norway. This conference has been a top venue for Arctic politics in the past years and therefore provided the perfect framework for a science-politics exchange. The “Young Politicians” are a group of enthusiastic high school kids from Northern Norway, who are interested in improving the communities in which they live through politics. During this one-day event, they learned about climate change and its impacts from the global to the local scale.

Chapter 3: APECS Online Activities and Publications

3.1. APECS International Online Conference 2016

The APECS Online Conference 2016, entitled “Polar Science: Through New Eyes,” took place on 18 May 2016 from 08:50 GMT to 21:20 GMT. It was a great success, with over 100 audience members registered, and a full day of presentations about polar research. The presenters engaged in scientific dialogues, and represented multiple disciplines and backgrounds, providing new research perspectives in their field of research. We would like to thank all of our presenters and those who tuned in. Special thanks to José Xavier (Session 2) and Rasmus Gjedssø Bertelsen (Session 4) for their inspiring keynote presentations in the successful second year of our global APECS online conference series for early career scientists. The recipients of the best presentation awards were:

- **Jesse Colangelo** (McGill University, Canada) - "*Sluggish viral dynamics in Arctic hypersaline spring sediments*" (Session 4)
- **Lavenia Ratnarajah** (Institute for Marine and Antarctic Studies, University of Tasmania, Australia) - "*The biogeochemical role of Baleen whales in Southern Ocean nutrient cycling*" (Session 1). The Antarctic prize is provided thanks to funding from Antarctic Science Ltd.

With increased attention on the changing polar environment and the future challenges this will bring, the conference conveyed the broad range of new research currently being conducted internationally. Sessions covered a range of disciplines, including Oceanography, Biology, History, Policy, Education, Geology, Atmosphere, and Climate Research, and were split into five sessions, depending on presenter time zones.

Session	Speaker	Registration # ¹	Attendee # ¹
Session 1: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Oceanography / sea ice ● Biological - marine, freshwater, terrestrial ● Cultural / historical / policy / education 	Speakers and presentations list	82	47
Session 2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cultural / historical / policy / education ● Keynote presentation: Jose Xavier ● Biological - marine, freshwater, terrestrial 	Speaker and presentation list	65	42
Session 3 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Oceanography / sea ice ● Geological / environmental / terrestrial / cryospheric Environments 	Speakers and presentations list	48	28
Session 4	Speakers and presentations list	54	20

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Keynote presentation: Rasmus Bertelsen • Geological / environmental / terrestrial / cryospheric Environments • Biological - marine, freshwater, terrestrial 			
Session 5 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Oceanography / sea ice • Atmospheric / Climatology • Cultural / historical / policy / education 	Speakers and presentations list	51	18

3.2. APECS Webinars

Table 3.2: Overview of all open APECS Webinars 2015-2016.

Date	Title	Speaker	Registration # ¹	Attendee # ¹
Career Development Webinars				
18 Apr 2016	SCAR-COMNAP-APECS-Webinar: Writing for Success! Preparing winning fellowship applications	Multiple	163	59
22 Apr 2016	Meeting your Outreach Goals with Strategic Science Communication	Kristin Timm	59	24
19 Sept 2016	Social Media for Marine and Antarctic Scientists	Indi Hodgson-Johnston	9	6 online + 40 in Hobart
22 Sept 2016	Understanding the ecological power of communication: Culture & nature tourism contexts	Tema Milstein	38	12
APECS-WWRP-Polar Prediction Project Webinar Series				
22/09/2015	APECS - WWRP - Polar Prediction Project Webinar Series Part 3: The Antarctic Automatic Weather Station Network	Matthew A. Lazzara	25	10
USAPECS Webinar Series				
06/04/2016	Data Visualization	Rob Simmon	137	60
19/04/2016	Boiling Down Your Message	Twila Moon and Daniella Scalice	74	35
02/05/2016	Outreach from Afar: Follow-A-Researcher in the Field	Kit Hamley & Charles Rodda	16	9
17/05/2016	Getting Into Schools: Building Bridges & Designing Activities with Teachers	Morgan Seag	39	15
31/05/2016	Broadening Your Impact & Addressing NSF Funding Criteria with Polar-ICE	Liesl Hotaling, Carrie Ferraro	49	24

09/06/2016	The Art and Science of Blogging	Mia Bennett	54	20
21/06/2016	Writing for Media and the General Public	Jeff Richardson	53	27

¹ Minimum number of attendees. Several webinars connected to classrooms and / or meeting rooms where groups of participants shared one screen / log-in.

3.3. Arctic Snapshots

Arctic Snapshots 2016
Across the Arctic Ocean

Arctic Snapshots are online webinars between researchers in Arctic earth, biological, and social sciences at different field stations. The project was launched by APECS in 2015 aiming to connect the Arctic stations to each other in order to share knowledge about the region and provide an opportunity for interdisciplinary and interinstitutional networking by creating a forum for joint reflection on moments of encountering the Arctic through research.

The Arctic Snapshots 2016 online session organized on 14 July 2016 and chaired by Yulia Zaika was able to connect 2 stations in Canada and Russia: Churchill Northern Studies Centre (Churchill, Canada) and Khibiny Educational and Scientific Station (Murmansk Region, Russia). There was an interdisciplinary session where stations were able to introduce themselves to each other and a group of meteorologists from Khibiny Station gave presentations about climate and weather conditions in the Arctic. The session connected groups of scientists and students in two Arctic areas with around 10-15 people each. Moreover, this year's event was made open to anyone interested and it accommodated more than 20 people online from Canada, Russia, USA, Peru, Brazil, United Kingdom, Norway, Germany, Austria and even Antarctica!

3.4. Figure Friday and APECS International Polar Week Figure Competition 2016

APECS started [Figure Friday](#) originally as a bi-weekly event that gives APECS members the opportunity to reach out and showcase their work among other polar researchers and enthusiasts. Members were encouraged to submit a figure from their ongoing or published work with summaries of their research or the one that looks the coolest to be showcased on the APECS website and social media. In September 2016, this project was turned into a [Figure Competition](#) as part of the APECS International Polar Week September 2016 that received 10 entries. The best 3 were awarded a prize. Winners were:

1st place: **Noémie Ross** and the 'A Frozen Ground Cartoon' team

A SUBJECT ADDRESSED IN A FROZEN-GROUND CARTOON PROJECT, SUPPORTED BY IPA

IN NORTHERN URALS **Permafrost processes** are affecting **REINDEER HUSBANDRY**

Directly

Thawing of the active layer in summer

Probabilities of tabeyization (weakening of soil under mechanical impact of herd)

Use of thawing layer for short-term storage of food

Indirectly

Travelling with sledge complicated

Impact on reindeer behavior through changes in vegetation and landscape

Hydrological conditions (lakes and ponds) are likely to change

SOURCE: Iatmin, K.V., Hobbach, J.O., Permafrost and indigenous land use in the northern Urals: Komi and Nenets reindeer husbandry, Polar Science (2016).
Illustrated by Noémie Ross. noemieross@gmail.com

2nd place: **Mathieu Casado**, University of Paris, Saclay

3rd place: **Ruth C. Heindel**, Dartmouth College

3.5. APECS International Polar Week Fieldwork Photo Competition 2016

During the APECS International Polar Week Spring 2016, APECS organized a [fieldwork photo competition](#), where APECS members were encouraged to submit photos and later vote for the prettiest, funniest, most interesting photo. We received 57 photos and after the voting the following [3 winners received a prize](#):

1st Prize: **Adrian Dahood**
(George Mason University,
United States)

2nd Prize: **Nathaniel B Dkhar** (The Energy and
Resources Institute, India)

3rd Prize: **Francoise Amélineau** (University of
Montpellier, France)

3.6. Digital Outreach

APECS has used a range of digital platforms to communicate with members over the past year. Communication tools available range from traditional one way communication channels such as web presence and newsletters, through to interactive online events, and a range of social media accounts.

The website acts as an official platform, ensuring that news and organisational information are always available at apecs.is. The site anchors the APECS online presence, and is the place where news and events are advertised and collated into archives of past activity. The most popular posts on the APECS site over the past year were about the Annual Online Conference (Call for Abstracts "Polar Science: Through New Eyes"), Polar Week activities (APECS Polar Week Photo Contest 2016 voting until 20 March), and Fellowship opportunities (IASC Fellowship Program 2016, SCAR and COMNAP Fellowships, CCAMLR scholarships). Many such items were also shared via the monthly newsletter, where the popular items over the past year related to funding circulars, or nominations for APECS members to sit on SCAR committees.

Webinars are another useful tool for digital outreach. These usually take the format of an invited speaker, with questions invited from the audience during and afterwards. Webinars are also recorded and posted on the APECS Vimeo channel as a resource for future use, and for those in other time zones. The most popular webinars over the past year dealt with soft skills, such as poster design, or funding application tips. The online conference was also popular, and ran over 5 sessions, with 32 presentations from 13 countries presenting to an audience of 113. This was useful for allowing members all over the world to learn from each other, and provided outreach between members in different areas and disciplines.

For reaching a broader, non-scientific audience, APECS has made use of Reddit. Also known as 'the front page of the internet', Reddit features forums with a wide range of topics – both general and scientific - and acts as a digital soapbox, where all manner of people browse, and upvote or downvote posts. Two APECS "Ask me anything" (AMA) events were held during Polar week Fall 2015 and Spring 2016, first in the general forums (members from

USA) and then in the science forums (members from UK and USA). There was much more engagement the second time around when the science forum was used, and the questions asked were much more sophisticated. The thread attracted 1911 votes and made it to the front page of reddit, thus bringing the topic of polar research to the attention of a much wider, non-polar audience. This platform is useful for engaging with those outside the normal reach of polar research circles.

Twitter and Facebook are also used by APECS. Twitter is useful for maintaining networks, both with individuals and other organisations. Popular tweets over the past year related to science findings and APECS events. APECS maintains both a Facebook page - an official communication channel, where APECS makes the posts - and a moderated group - where members join, and anyone can share news and info. The most popular posts over the past year related to opportunities to monitor wildlife, and upcoming conferences.

There are many tools available for online communication, ranging

from more static options like a website, to interactive platforms like Facebook and Twitter. It is important to choose the medium depending on your goals, be that to inform, engage in dialogue, or create a platform to start discussions. It also depends who you want to reach – members, general public, other scientists, educators etc. - and for what reason. For instance, if you want to know what sorts of questions are being asked of polar researchers today (i.e. major areas of public interest), the Reddit AMA platform is useful. To communicate specialist subject knowledge with members, webinars are a great tool. To keep in touch with members and make it easy for them to access information, sharing on multiple platforms like Facebook and Twitter is useful.

The APECS experience has shown that digital outreach does have real strengths in a real-world context, helping to connect members all over the world. It is important that communication channels evolve along with technology, but if you do that, and use several channels, then these tools really can make crossing borders quicker, easier, and more accessible than before.

3.7. APECS Publications

National Committee	Title
Publication / Report	
International	<p>Majaneva, S., Hamon, G., Fugmann, G., Lisowska, M. and J. Baeseman (2016): Where are they now? – A case study of the impact of international travel support for early career Arctic researchers. Polar Science, Vol. 10, Issue 3, p. 382 - 394. http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.polar.2016.06.001</p> <p>Vingerhagen, R, Bradley, A., Mariash, H., Nielsen, H., Vick-Majors, T., Moore, J.S., Zaika, Y. Strey, S. and G. Fugmann (2016): APECS Strategic Plan 2016-2020</p> <p>Vick-Majors, T. J., S. Engelbertz, and G. Fugmann (2016), Focus on the future of polar research, Eos, 97, doi:10.1029/2016EO042993. Published on 8 January 2016.</p> <p>Zaika, Y., Beck, I., Badhe, R., Dubinenkov, I., Kuznetsova, E., Pope, A, Rachold, V. and J. Xavier (2015): APECS Organisational Review Recommendations Report.</p> <p>APECS (2015): APECS Annual Report 2014-2015.</p> <p>Sharp, L, Paquin, K., Fugmann, G. and the APECS Nordic Team (2015): APECS Nordic Project 2013 - 2015 - Bridging Early Career Researchers and Indigenous Peoples in Nordic Countries - Final Report 2015. APECS.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • English Version • Russian Version (translation by Yulia Zaika) <p>APECS Newsletter October 2015 - September 2016 (published monthly)</p>
Brazil	APECS-Brazil Newsletter 2015.2 - Magazine for science outreach and activities related to the Brazilian Polar Science. It's published twice a year since 2010.
Chile	Maturana, C., Bastias, J., and S. Ruiz (2016): APECS Chile. A Polar Science Opportunity for Young Researchers . In: ILAIA - Advances in Chilean Antarctic Science. No 3, p. 34 - 35.
France	APECS France - Rapport d'activités 2015 .
India	<p>Polar Bytes Bulletin - a public outreach initiative by Indian Polar Research Network (IPRN) to create awareness on polar science activities in India.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Polar Bytes Bulletin Volume 1(2), September 2015 • Polar Bytes Bulletin Volume 2 (1), June 2016.
United Kingdom	UK Polar Network blog
Oral Presentations	
Switzerland	Presentation about APECS Switzerland during the Cryosphere Session at the Swiss Geoscience Meeting in Basel (November 2015).
Germany	<p>APECS presentations by APECS Germany at the:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordination Workshop of the German Research Priority Programm for Antarctic Research (SPP 1158), 01 October 2015, Frankfurt, Germany • Annual Meeting of the German SCAR/IASC National Committee, 19 - 20 Mai 2016, Bremen, Germany;

Brazil	Affonso, S. F.; Zanin, A. C.; Kiem, S. Z.; Costa, E. S.; Rios, F.S. Construção do Conhecimento Científico através de Experimentações sobre as Regiões Polares. XII Congresso Nacional de Educação (EDUCERE). Curitiba, Brazil. 26-29 October 2015. Available at: http://educere.pucpr.br/pt/publicacoes-anais-do-congresso.html
France	Clément-Chastel C., Dansereau V., Lamarque G., Lescarmonier L., Schiavone S., APECS France, un réseau de jeunes chercheurs et médiateurs des régions polaires, 12 ^o journées scientifiques du CNFRA (oral presentation – may 2016) 2015
Oceania	APECS Oceania presentation at the APECS Workshop prior to the SCAR 2016 Open Science Conference in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia (August 2016).
Poster Presentations	
International	Vingerhagen, R., Fugmann, G. and Y. Zaika (2016): APECS education and outreach activities for shaping the future of polar research . Poster presentation at the University of the Arctic Congress 2016, September 2016, St. Petersburg, Russia. Poster about APECS Interantional at the EU-PolarNet Townhall Meeting in Brussels, Belgium on 27 September 2016
Finland	Poster and 10 min presentation about what APECS is at the Nordic Oikos conference 2.-4.2.2016, Turku
Bulgaria	Sabeva, R., Dochev, D., Velev, St., Apostolova, D., Trifonova, I. (2015). APECS Bulgaria: Association of Polar Early-Career Scientists. National conference with international participation “Geo Sciences 2015”.
Germany	Poster about APECS International at the Polartagung der Deutschen Gesellschaft für Polarforschung (DGP), 07 - 10 September 2015, Munich, Germany

Chapter 4: APECS Project Highlights

APECS started as part of the International Polar Year (IPY) 2007-2008 efforts to involve early career researchers in international polar science. The next five years of growth is outlined by the 2016-2020 Strategic Plan. Additionally, as APECS is approaching nearly a decade of establishment, a new award was introduced to recognize outstanding individuals who have served as mentors.

4.1. APECS Strategic Plan 2016 - 2020

The [APECS Strategic Plan for 2016-2020](#) sets out five key areas for APECS to concentrate on in the next five years in order to ensure that APECS continues to thrive and inspire:

1. Capacity Building
2. Cutting Edge of Information Assessment
3. Outreach
4. Establish a Structure to Grow Sustainably
5. Improve Internal Functions

APECS
Association of Polar
Early Career Scientists
2016-2020 Strategic Plan

The plan is a result of discussions and consultations arising from the [APECS Organizational Review \(2015\)](#), [APECS World Summit \(2015\)](#), and a survey sent to the APECS National Committees and Leadership and we thank everyone who provided feedback as part of these processes. We also thank our Advisory Committee for their continued advice and input to the strategic plan.

4.2. APECS International Mentorship Award 2016

This year, APECS decided to recognize and honor the efforts of their mentors within the international polar science community. This new award was created to acknowledge the time and energy that mentors dedicate to early career researchers each year, and their efforts in building a supportive community. The inaugural award was presented to David Carlson during the Arctic Observing Summit 2016 in Fairbanks, Alaska this March.

Dave's support during the International Polar Year was instrumental in the

establishment of APECS and his mentorship over the years has helped APECS grow into the organization it is today.

We received an astounding number of letters nominating Dave for this award, describing Dave as a “mentor of historical proportions.” These letters also featured personal stories – how someone, after a chance meeting with Dave at a conference – gained a valuable and insightful mentor in research, outreach, and life.

Dave has again and again championed outreach and education as a critical part of scientific research. His dedication to making sure the work of polar scientists is shared with diverse audiences has certainly been a boon to the field of polar research as a whole. He inspired many polar researchers and generations to come to do education and outreach and to communicate their research about the Polar regions.

Dave also has a remarkable skill for bringing people together, and he has channeled that to creating opportunities around the world for early career scientists. His incredible dedication to mentoring both the APECS organization and individual early career researchers has opened an untold number of doors and shaped dozens of careers.

APECS would like to thank Dave for everything that he has done as a mentor for both our organization and for so many of us as individuals. The APECS International Mentorship Award is a small token of our enormous gratitude for Dave’s time, wisdom, and passion over the years.

David Carlson is currently the Director of the World Climate Research Programme (WCRP), where he facilitates analysis and prediction of Earth system variability and change with relevance, benefit and value to society. He is co-founder and co-Chief Editor, with H. Pfeiffenberger (Alfred Wegener Institute), of Earth System Science Data, an international data publication journal. Dave supported the establishment of APECS during his tenure as Director of the International Polar Year (IPY) International Programme Office, where he organised, managed, coordinated, represented and supported the international interdisciplinary science program. Previously he was the Director of the Atmospheric Technology Division at NCAR, Director of the Tropical Ocean Global Atmosphere (TOGA) Coupled Ocean Atmosphere Response Experiment (COARE) International Project Office, and Associate Professor in the College of Oceanography at Oregon State University.

Award Committee (2015-2016):

- **Zuzanna Swirad**, Durham University, UK (Chair)
- **Jennifer Cooper**, Cornell University, USA
- **Gunnar Mar Gunnarson**, Cambridge University, UK
- **Mar Fernandez Mendez**, Norwegian Polar Institute, Norway
- **Ruth Vingerhagen**, University of St. Andrews, UK
- **Matthias Wietz**, University of Oldenburg, Germany
- **Sara Strey**, University of Illinois at Urbana Champaign, USA
- **Gerlis Fugmann**, APECS / UiT The Arctic University of Norway, Norway (ex-officio)

4.3. APECS-CLiC Where are they now

The project “Where are they now?” investigated the subsequent

career paths of early career researchers (ECRs) that received support and funding from the International Arctic Science Committee (IASC) since the start of the most recent IPY (2007-2008) and beyond.

The goal of this project was to assess, how IASC support impacted careers and to find ways to further enhance the support and training of ECRs provided by the Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS), the WCRP Climate and Cryosphere Project and the IASC. The project was a contribution to the [Third International Conference on Arctic Research Planning \(ICARP III\)](#). The final project results were recently published in the Journal “Polar Science”:

Majaneva, S., Hamon, G., Fugmann, G., Lisowska, M. and J. Baeseman (2016): Where are they now? – A case study of the impact of international travel support for early career Arctic researchers. *Polar Science*, Vol. 10, Issue 3, p. 382 - 394. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.polar.2016.06.001>

4.4. Projects from the APECS National Committees

APECS National Committees have been very active again over the last year and developed several projects within their countries. Below you can find a selection of their activities and you can read the full reports from the National Committees on the [APECS website](#).

National Committee	Project
APECS Brazil	<i>Training Workshop</i> . “The polar regions inside the classrooms” 26 October 2015
	<i>Course of Continuing Education</i> . Integrating air, water, soil, astronomy and the food chain in Antarctica and the Arctic, offered for teachers from public school, 2016, Curitiba, PR, Brazil
	<i>Distance education course</i> . We created and held an extension distance education course for teachers “Antártica ou Antártida? How to include the Antarctic science at schools”. The course is comprised of factual information, activities, videos, animations, games, and discussion groups. All the video lessons are available on our YouTube channel and are already subtitled into English. Periodic publications about “Antártica ou Antártida?” are on Facebook .
APECS Canada	<i>APECS Canada - ASA (ArcticNet Student Association) Mentor Award</i> (see highlights section below).
APECS France	<i>APRES 3 – Ondes et Flocons</i> . Ondes et Flocon is the educational component of the APRES3 research program run at the Laboratoire de Glaciologie et Géophysique de l'Environnement (LGGE), which aims at improving predictions in precipitations over Antarctica. Students from the participating classes are presented the opportunity to become a researcher's apprentice. Thematic cards are used to teach them the links between snow, the climate of the Antarctic and sea level rise. Blogs present the work

	<p>and fieldwork of Antarctic researchers. Students can also realize mini-scientific projects with the help of an educational team and interact with researchers as well as with other classes involved in the project.</p> <p><i>Savanturiers des Glaces</i>: is an educational program throughout research for classes of any level mostly about the impact of climate change. The general idea behind the program is to link a young researcher with a class and build a project about its research, its fieldwork, etc. Participating students have to apply scientific rigour to solve a given problem or question. In doing so, they are encouraged to develop their critical mind, their will of exploring the unknown, as well as their innovative and collaborative capabilities. At the end of the school year, classes meet and share their experiences.</p> <p><i>Draw me the future</i>: Launched in 2015, Draw me the future is intended for kids from all over the world to exchange positive messages regarding the future of their planet, and the future of polar regions in particular. With the idea of overcoming language barriers, all correspondences between the participating classes will take place as drawing exchanges, photograph exchanges, games, etc. This year, a correspondence was initiated between two classes from France and Guinea. We intend to enlarge this activity in partnership with other APECS national committee in coming years.</p>
APECS Italy	<i>Project Reset- Research and education Svalbard experience</i> . The RESEt project will last three years and includes several disciplines of school. RESEt is a project of scientific nature, of exploration and research...pointed toward our goal of learning and personal enrichment. The principle objectives consist not only of the Arctic trip, but to work hard and succeed with determination and dedication to achieve a big goal. The journal of our visit and exploration of Svalbard is just "the tip of the iceberg" in our initiative. Foremost, it is an occasion of growth and empowerment. In the first two years of RESEt we have been busy searching for finding and sponsors. We have also been studying the Arctic regions.
APECS Portugal	<i>"Ciência às Claras"</i> . Monthly activity. This education and outreach activity takes place every 15th day of each month. On this day, a member of APECS explains in a simplified way an scientific polar-related article, making easily understood by people of all ages and backgrounds. This activity has shown an increasing number of online views (each article is currently viewed by an average of 560 people. The last second article has in fact reached nearly 800 viewers. The articles are placed in our website and spread and shared through Facebook.
Russian Polar Initiative	<i>Training program for students from MGIMO - Moscow Institute of Foreign Affairs</i> . Analytical reviews on international affairs in the Arctic with focus on Russian Arctic . Interviews with the opinion leaders in Russian Polar Science.
APECS Turkey	One of the significant project conducted by Istanbul Technical University (ITU) Polar Research Center (PolReC), started in 2015, was establishing "Polar Research Clubs" under 26 different middle schools. It is still an ongoing project and each club has about 15 students. In total, 400 middle school students have joined to the clubs. Simultaneously "University Students Polar Team" (PolSTeam) was established under the same university in 2015, provided information and floor for joining different activities with regard to polar research and studies. More than 150 university students joined PolSTeam. Following to the effectuation of these two formations, university students visit middle school clubs and students, convey their knowledge to juniors and respond to their questions.
UKPN	<u>Survey how organisations like UKPN can better support postdocs in their research and life</u> . The project aims to look into trying to improve support and address current issues for postdocs through this year within the UK research framework, and to see what the community thinks are the most pertinent questions and issues that are worth tackling. The survey was organized by the UK Polar Network and the UK Arctic and Antarctic Partnership
USAPECS	<i>Polar Film Festival</i> (see highlights section below)

Highlights:

Award for APECS France December 2015

In the context of the COP21 that occurred in December 2015 and on the idea of the French Minister of Foreign Affairs, the foundation Yves Rocher, under the aegis of the Foundation of France, created a special "Climate" award to its prize "Women of the Earth" 2016. On March 3rd 2016, the APECS-France association, led by a board of women, received in Paris this award for the organization of the French Polar Week, that sensitizes thousands of children about polar sciences.

This award is an amazing recognition for the energy and time given by all the young polar researchers, and a strong encouragement to pursue the educational initiatives : this endowment will allow APECS-France to organize its very first physical Polar Week event, in October 2016.

Congratulations to all !!

APECS Canada - ASA Mentor Award 2015 December 2015

Dr. Chris Furgal (third from the right) and his team of nominators celebrate the 2015 APECS Canada-ASA Mentor Award on stage. Photo by Maéva Gauthier/ArcticNet.

Dr. Chris Furgal, Associate Professor at Trent University (Peterborough, ON), won the APECS Canada-ArcticNet Student Association Mentor Award 2015.

The Mentor Award review committee received six nominations in September, which it assessed and ranked throughout the month of October. During two conference calls the committee reached a consensus-based decision.

Chris was nominated by his graduate students, while colleagues and community leaders provided a number of letters of support. His nomination stood out among the six excellent submissions, although the committee noted that all nominations were of excellent quality. You can learn more about Chris's research here and about his Health Environment and Indigenous Communities Research Group here.

Chris accepted the award during the ArcticNet ASM 2015 meeting banquet on Thursday, December 10th, 2015. Award Committee Chair Dr. Nikolaus Gantner (APECS Canada) and Rudy Riedlsperger (ArcticNet SA) introduced the awardee to the 700+ delegates.

During the ceremony, the inaugural winner of the award, Eric Loring (Inuit Tapiriit Kanatami) was spontaneously invited on stage to hand over the prize, a photo book filled with pictures and messages from the supporters of his nomination, on behalf of those closely working with Chris (see below).

We would like to thank all individuals and organizations who contributed to the six nominations for this 2015 award competition.

For the 2015 Awards Committee, Dr. Nikolaus Gantner (Chair, 2015 APECS Canada-ASA Awards Committee)

Polar Film Fest 2016

September 2016

During Polar Weeks, the USAPECS Board piloted a Virtual Polar Film Fest to harness the power of inspiring and exciting educational videos that are already available online and repackaged them for Polar Week in September 2016.

Video nominations were crowd-sourced from the polar research community. We received more than 100 submissions (already posted on Vimeo and YouTube) of both amateur and professional videos of varying lengths, some of which covered serious topics and others that were more light-hearted (e.g., "Happy Feet"). Videos were reviewed and organized into four themes, each of which was highlighted on a day of the Film Fest: Frozen Worlds, Partly Frozen Mostly Cute, Climate & Connections, and People at the Poles.

During Polar Week, APECS members hosted in-person and virtual watch parties where groups gathered to watch selected videos and/or playlists and discuss what they were watching with APECS experts. In-person watch parties were held in Boulder (CO), Fairbanks (AK), Orono (ME), Whitehorse (YT), Potsdam (DE), and Cambridge (UK). Virtual watch parties were hosted by Alice Bradley, Mia Bennett, Morgan Seag, and David Schutt on Twitter using the #PolarFilmFest hashtag. Playlists were also widely disseminated to APECS members, APECS partners (including Polar-ICE), and over social media.

Overall, Polar Film Fest videos racked up over 24,000 views, contributing an average of 8% to the total views on the films featured on the playlists. There were 184 tweets using the #PolarFilmFest during the week, with participants from around the world contributing.

The 2016 Virtual Polar Film Fest was organized by Allen Pope, Alice Bradley, Ariel Morrison, David Schutt, Olivia Lee, and Alex Thornton with further help from the USAPECS Board and APECS members.

Chapter 5: Partners and Sponsors

5.1. APECS Formal Partnerships (MoUs)

- Alfred Wegener Institute Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research (26 September 2016)
- Murmansk Arctic State University (11 July 2016)
- International Glaciological Society (IGS) (21 February 2016)
- Polar Educators International – (renewed 15 January 2016)
- International Network for Terrestrial Research and Monitoring in the Arctic (INTERACT) (15 December 2015)
- Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research and International Arctic Science Committee (renewed on 16 April 2013)
- Permafrost Young Researchers Network (PYRN) and International Permafrost Association (IPA) - 18 August 2012
- International Association for Cryospheric Sciences (23 September 2011)
- Arctic Frontiers (5 October 2010)
- University of the Arctic and the International Antarctic Institute (9 June 2010)
- International Association of Arctic Social Scientists and Social Sciences and Humanities Antarctic Research Exchange (24 September 2010)

These groups often provide in kind support in the form of advertising, high-level endorsement, meeting space at conferences, travel support for APECS members.

5.2. Sponsors

Thank you from the entire APECS leadership to the various sponsors for helping us Shape the Future of Polar Research over the last year and in the years to come!

International Activities

APECS International Directorate

The main costs associated with running APECS are associated with supporting our International Directorate Office currently located in Tromsø, Norway with the full-time APECS Executive Director. We are very grateful to the [Research Council of Norway](#), the [UiT The Arctic University of Norway](#), and the [Norwegian Polar Institute](#) for providing the finances needed to keep all our activities centrally coordinated and running efficiently.

In addition, [Murmansk Arctic State University](#), funds a part-time APECS Officer for the APECS International Directorate located in Murmansk, Russia from July 2016 to February 2017. APECS is very grateful for this additional staff support.

Activity, event and other support

APECS wants to specifically acknowledge the financial support by [Antarctic Science Ltd.](#) for Antarctic activities within APECS. This support allowed APECS not only support for the APECS Workshop at the SCAR Open Science Conference 2016 but also support [13 APECS members with partial travel awards to attend Antarctic-related conferences in 2016.](#)

[Arctic Portal](#) in Akureyri, Iceland for continuous in-kind website support for and hosting of the APECS website.

Travel support for APECS leaders / representatives and other early career researchers to attend various meetings and events was provided by (not an exhaustive list):

- **Research Council of Norway; UiT – The Arctic University of Norway; Norwegian Polar Institute** for the travel of the APECS Executive Director as part of the funding for the APECS International Directorate Office
- **Climate and Cryosphere (CliC) Project** for travel to the CliC SSC Meeting 2016
- **Ice Sheet Mass Balance and Sea Level (ISMSS)** for travel of [four early career researchers to the SCAR Open Science Conference 2016.](#)
- **German SCAR / IASC Committee** for travel of an APECS representative to attend their meeting in May 2016
- **Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research (SCAR)** for travel support of several APECS representatives on SCAR groups
- **Nordnorsk Vitensenteret** in Tromsø for funding for Arctic Frontiers Science for Schools providing travel support for 3 early career researchers to present at the event

Support from APECS to APECS activities

Despite having only a small budget, APECS was able to support several of its own activities:

- APECS Executive Committee Meeting 2016 in Fairbanks, Alaska (March 2016)
- APECS representatives attending the SCAR / IASC Think Tank Meeting in Potsdam, Germany (February 2016) and the European Polar Board Meetings in November 2015 in Vienna, Austria and in April 2016 in Stockholm, Sweden
- APECS-ASA Data Management Workshop at the Polar Data Forum II in October 2015 in Waterloo, Canada
- Permafrost Young Researchers Workshop 2016 at the International Conference on Permafrost 2016 in Potsdam, Germany
- Prizes for the APECS Online Conference 2016
- Prizes for the APECS International Polar Week Photo Contest 2016
- Prizes for the APECS International Polar Week Figure Contest 2016
- Workshops and activities organized by APECS Brazil, APECS Portugal, the UK Polar Network and USAPECS

5.3. Partners and Sponsors of the APECS National Committees

The APECS National Committees are working with a number of partners and were able to receive funding and in-kind support for several of their events and activities.

APECS Belgium

In-kind support:

- Belgian Science Policy Office (BELSPO) provided in-kind support for our meeting

APECS Brazil

Financial / In-kind support:

- APECS Event Funding (350 euros for the Ice break)
- University of Brasília (UNB): Our main partner, they host the Symposium, and provided all the infra-structure.
- SECIRM/PROANTAR - Secretariat of the Interministerial Commission for the Sea Resources and Brazilian Antarctic Program: Help with transportation in Brasília and accommodation.
- Federal and State Universities from the APECS-Brazil members: Indirectly contribution.
- CNPQ, National Counsel of Technological and Scientific Development: Financial support.
- FAPDF, Federal District Research Support Foundation: Financial support.

Regular partners:

- Universidade Estadual do Rio Grande do Sul (UERGS, São Luiz Gonzaga, RS, Brazil)
- Universidade Estadual do Rio Grande do Sul (UERGS, Sananduva, RS, Brazil)
- Centro Educacional Marista Lúcia Mayvorne (Florianópolis, SC, Brazil)
- Universidade Federal do Paraná (UFPR) – Educational Resources, PROEXT Polar regions
- Faculdade de Pimenta Bueno (FAP, Oimenta Bueno, RO, Brazil)
- Colégio Estadual Tereza Francescutti (Canoas, RS, Brazil)
- Colégio Maria Auxiliadora (Canoas, RS, Brazil)

- Escola Estadual de Ensino Fundamental e Médio Juscelino Kubistchek de Oliveira (Alta Floresta D'Oeste, RO, Brazil)
- Colégio Estadual Wolfram Metzler (São Leopoldo, RS, Brazil)
- E.E.E.F. Alcides João Gradashi (Soledade, RS, Brazil)
- All the universities and institutions related to the members of the Brazilian National Committee

APECS Bulgaria

Regular partners:

- Bulgarian Antarctic Institute
- British Council
- Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski"

APECS Canada

Financial and in-kind support:

- PYRN (Permafrost Young Researchers Network) (financial – to ASA-APECS Student Day Social)
- AINA (Arctic Institute of North America) (financial – donated prizes to ASA-APECS Student Day Social)
- Summit Environmental (financial - food for panel discussion)
- Yukon College (in-kind, space for panel discussion and connecting emails by Science Adventures for Polar Week webinars)
- Skookum Jim Friendship Centre (financial and in-kind – space for panel discussion, food for panel discussion, sponsorships for youth to attend from communities)
- Nunavut Arctic College (in-kind - space for film night and poster session, printing posters)

Regular Partner:

- [Polar Knowledge Canada](#) – providing advice and recommendations for student internship candidates

APECS Chile

Regular Partner:

- Instituto Antártico Chileno (INACH)

APECS France

The prize awarded by the Yves Rocher Foundation will contribute to the organization of the 2016 Polar Week events.

APECS Germany

Financial and in-kind support:

- DFG (German Research Foundation); financial (travel support)
- German Priority Program for Antarctic Research (SPP 1158); financial (travel support)

Indian Polar Research Network

Regular Partners:

- [National Centre for Antarctic and Ocean Research](#)
- [Wildlife Institute of India](#)

APECS Italy

Regular Partner:

- National Research Council

APECS Japan

Regular partners:

- [Japan Consortium for Arctic Environmental Research](#) (JCAR)
- [Arctic Research Center of Hokkaido University](#)

APECS Netherlands

Financial support:

- 'Pool tot Pool'
- Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research (NWO)

APECS Oceania

In-kind support:

- APECS Oceania was supported in kind by the Bottom of the Earth Society (BOTES) at the Institute for Marine and Antarctic Studies (IMAS), with venue and organising help provided for the March 2016 quiz night.

Regular Partners:

- APECS Oceania would like to acknowledge the ongoing support of Antarctica New Zealand and the COMNAP Secretary

APECS Poland

Financial and In-kind support for APECS Poland Workshop:

- Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research - SCAR (financial)
- Centre for Polar Studies, Poland (both financial and in-kind)
- Polish Polar Consortium (in-kind)
- Faculty of Earth Sciences and Spatial Management, University of Maria Curie-Skłodowska, Lublin, Poland (in-kind)

Regular Partners:

- [Committee on Polar Research](#), Polish Academy of Science, [PL] (APECS Poland representative invited to plenary meetings twice a year)
- [Polish Polar Consortium](#)
- [Centre for Polar Studies](#)

APECS Portugal:

Financial and in-kind Support

- APECS International – covered costs for traveling and accommodations expenses during the latest IV APECS Portugal workshop held in Évora.
- PROPOLAR – Portuguese Polar Programme covered APECS member's fee during the Portuguese Polar Conference in Évora.
- University of Évora – provided the coffee break during the Workshop.

UKPN

Financial support:

- APECS Event Funding
- Cambridge-EnvEast Doctoral Alliance (CEEDA)

In-kind support:

- The Association of Science Educators (ASE) for waiving event fees and for providing workshop space at their annual conference in Birmingham.
- The Challenger Society for a jointly-hosted workshop at their annual conference in Liverpool.
- Leeds Science Festival for an invitation to conduct workshops on polar climate change in conjunction with the International Polar Foundation

Regular Partners:

- International Polar Foundation
- British Antarctic Survey
- National Environmental Research Council (NERC) Arctic Office
- UK Arctic and Antarctic Partnership (UKAAP)
- UK National Committee for Antarctic Research (UKNCAR)
- The Foundation for the Good Governance of International Spaces (Our Spaces)

APECS United States (USAPECS)**Financial and In-kind support:**

- AGU Cryosphere Focus Group helped fund the panel and pub meet-up held at the fall meeting.
- International Glaciological Society provided a room to hold the panel at the La Jolla symposium.

Regular Partners:

- AGU Cryosphere Focus Group
- International Glaciological Society
- Arctic Research Consortium of the United States (ARCUS)

5.4. International Opportunities for APECS members 2015-2016

APECS has worked again with several international partners to create opportunities for APECS members and early career researchers in general to get involved in international committees, workshops and meetings, or to be co-conveners for sessions at international conferences. A number of other early career researchers have already been involved in several committees for a longer period of time and have this year continued their participation in those. In addition, APECS (co-)organized presentations and poster awards at some conferences. APECS would like to thank all of our partners for offering these opportunities for early career researchers and for helping to support the career development of this next generation of Arctic and Antarctic leaders in research.

International Opportunity	Name and Affiliation
Early Career Researchers on International Committees <i>*indicates APECS representative</i>	
Created new in 2015-2016:	
ASSW 2017 Steering Committee	TJ Young (University of Cambridge / British Antarctic Survey, UK)
Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research (SCAR) Life Sciences (LS) Scientific Standing Group (SSG)	Fernanda Quaglio (Universidade Estadual Paulista, Brazil) Jeff Bowman (Lamont-Doherty Earth Observatory, United States) Henrik Christiansen (KU Leuven, Belgium)
International Arctic Science Committee (IASC) Fellowship Programme 2015-2016	Paul Zieger (Atmosphere WG) (Stockholm University, Sweden) Alek Petty (Cryosphere WG) (NASA Goddard Space Flight Center / University of Maryland, United States) Allison Fong (Marine WG) (Alfred Wegener Institute, Germany)

	<p>Justiina Dahl (Social and Human WG) (European University Institute, Italy)</p> <p>Scott Zolkos (Terrestrial WG) (University of Alberta, Canada)</p> <p>Yulia Zaika (ISIRA) (Lomonosov Moscow State University, Russia)</p>
POLAR 2018 International Scientific Organizing Committee	Ruth Vingerhagen (University of Cambridge, United Kingdom)
Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks (SAON) Review	Justiina Dahl (European University Institute, Italy)
Early Career Researchers Network of Networks (ECR-NoN)	<p>Gerlis Fugmann (Executive Committee) APECS / UiT The Arctic University of Norway)</p> <p>Heather Mariash (Council) (National Wildlife Research Centre, Canada)</p> <p>Hanne Nielsen (Future Earth Working Group) (University of Tasmania, Australia)</p>
SCAR Wikibomb " Women in Antarctica "	Rachel Downey (Naturmuseum Senckenberg, Germany)
Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research (SCAR) Expert Group on Birds and Marine Mammals (EG BAMB)	Jaimie Cleeland (University of Tasmania, Australia)
Longer-term representation continuing in 2015-2016:	
Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research (SCAR) Open Science Conference 2016 – International Scientific Organising Committee	Rachel Downey (Naturmuseum Senckenberg, Germany)
ISMAS (Ice Sheet Mass Balance and Sea Level) Steering Committee	Ellyn Enderlin (University of Maine, United States)
SCAR Astronomy & Astrophysics in Antarctica (AAA) Steering Committee	Jennifer Cooper (Cornell University, United States)
ICARP III (Third International Conference on Arctic Research Planning) Steering Committee	Sanna Majaneva (Linnaeus University, Sweden)
Southern Ocean Observing System (SOOS) Scientific Steering Committee (ex-officio)	Tosca Ballerini (Mediterranean Institute of Oceanography, France)
Polar Prediction Project Steering Group	Jonathan Day (University of Reading, United Kingdom)
International Network for Terrestrial Research and Monitoring in the Arctic (INTERACT) Transnational Access Board	Ruth Vingerhagen (University of St.Andrews, United Kingdom)
SCAR Antarctic Climate Change in the 21 st Century (AntClim21) Steering Committee	Alia Khan (University of Colorado Boulder, United States)
Arctic Frontiers Steering Committee	Gerlis Fugmann (APECS / UiT The Arctic University of Norway)

Early Career Researchers at International Meetings and Workshops

**represented APECS as invited observer at the meeting*

***attended as invited early career researchers*

ELOKA Workshop , 22 - 24 September 2015, Boulder, Colorado, USA	Nikolaus Gantner (University of Northern British Columbia, Canada)
CAFF CMBP Freshwater Group Workshop , 5 – 8 October 2015, Sonnerupgaard, Denmark	Heather Mariash (National Wildlife Research Centre, Canada)
Northern Contaminants Program (NCP) fall Management Committee meeting, 6 - 7 October 2016	Jennifer Provencher (Carleton University, Canada)
European Polar Board Meeting, 5 - 6 November 2015, Vienna, Austria	Yulia Zaika (Lomonosov Moscow State University, Russia)
12th CliC Steering Committee Meeting , 2 - 4 February 2016, Copenhagen, Denmark	Ekaterina Uryupova (University of Salford, United Kingdom)
CAFF Board Meeting, February 2016, Kirkenes, Norway	Gerlis Fugmann (APECS / UiT The Arctic University of Norway)
Arctic and Antarctic Think Tank , February 2016, Potsdam, Germany	Ruth Vingerhagen (University of St.Andrews, UK)
IASC Council Meeting 2016, March 2016, Fairbanks, Alaska, USA	Gerlis Fugmann (APECS / UiT The Arctic University of Norway)
UNDESA Expert Group Meeting on Emerging Issues, 5 - 6 April 2016, New York, United States	Gerlis Fugmann (APECS / UiT The Arctic University of Norway)
European Polar Board Meeting , 11 - 12 April 2016, Stockholm, Sweden	Heather Mariash (National Wildlife Research Centre, Canada)
German SCAR / IASC Meeting , 19 May 2016, Bremen, Germany	Heike Link (University of Kiel, Germany)
IPA Council Meeting, June 2016, Potsdam, Germany	Stefanie Weege (Alfred-Wegener-Institute, Germany) Gerlis Fugmann (APECS / UiT The Arctic University of Norway)
SCAR Delegate Meeting, 29 - 30 August 2016, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia	Gerlis Fugmann (APECS / UiT The Arctic University of Norway)
CAFF Board Meeting , 6 - 8 September 2016, Longyearbyen, Svalbard	Karolina Paquin
EU PolarNet Townhall Meeting , September 2016, Brussels, Belgium,	Henrik Christiansen (KU Leuven, Belgium)
Early Career Co-Conveners nominated by APECS for International Conferences	
SCAR Open Science Conference 2016, 20 - 30 August 2016, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia	Francois Massonnet (Catalan Institute of climate Sciences, Spain) Bernabé Moreno (Cientifica del Sur University, Peru)

	<p>Lara F. Perez (Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland, Denmark)</p> <p>Kristin Poinar (University of Washington, United States)</p> <p>Bertie Miles (Durham University, United Kingdom)</p> <p>Trista Vick-Majors (Montana State University, United States)</p> <p>Christel Hansen (Rhodes University, South Africa)</p> <p>Amna Jrrar (NYUAD, United Arab Emirates)</p> <p>Erik Behrens (National Institute of Water and Atmospheric Research, New Zealand)</p> <p>Yasmina M. Martos (British Antarctic Survey (NERC), United Kingdom)</p> <p>Elizabeth Petrie (University of Glasgow, United Kingdom)</p> <p>Jennifer Cooper (California State University Los Angeles/University of California Irvine, United States)</p> <p>Asparuh Kamburov (University of Mining and Geology "St. Ivan Rilski", Bulgaria)</p> <p>Shridhar Jawak (National Centre For Antarctic & Ocean Research, India)</p> <p>Nicole Hill (University of Tasmania, Australia)</p> <p>Jeff Bowman (Columbia University, United States)</p> <p>Chun Wie Chong (International Medical University, Malaysia)</p> <p>Michelle Shero (University of Alaska Anchorage, United States)</p> <p>Henrik Christiansen (KU Leuven, Belgium)</p> <p>Casey Youngflesh (Stony Brook University, United States)</p> <p>Anne Treasure (University of Cape Town, South Africa)</p> <p>Claudia Maturana (University of Chile, Chile)</p> <p>Jaimie Cleeland (University of Tasmania, Australia)</p> <p>Rachel Downey (Naturmuseum Senckenberg, Germany)</p> <p>Julie Schram (University of Alabama at Birmingham, United States)</p> <p>Camille Moreau (Université Libre de Bruxelles, Belgium)</p> <p>Kimberley Rain Miner (University of Maine, United States)</p> <p>Sune Tamm-Buckle (University of Akureyri, Iceland)</p> <p>Hanne Nielsen (University of Tasmania, Australia)</p> <p>Neelu Singh (National Centre for antarctic and Ocean Research, India)</p> <p>Oliver Thomas Hogg (British Antarctic Survey, United Kingdom)</p>
Presentation and Poster awards (co-)coordinated by APECS	
<p>Arctic Frontiers 2016 Early Career Poster Awards, 28 January 2016, Tromsø, Norway</p> <p>Poster Awards organized by APECS and Arctic Frontiers</p>	<p>OVERALL WINNER:</p> <p>Daria Gritsenko: Ukraine and the Arctic - Apples and Oranges?</p> <p>RUNNERS-UP:</p> <p>Melissa Brandner: Environmental Impact Assessment: It's in the DNA!</p>

	<p>Peter Leopold: After 1000 years of absence... - The worlds northernmost blue mussels (<i>Mytilus</i> sp.) population is once again thriving during the time of a rapidly changing Arctic</p> <p>Ilya Stepanov: The Northernmost Sea Route Development: Economic and Political Implications</p>
<p>SCAR Open Science Conference 2016, 20 - 30 August 2016, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia</p> <p>Poster Awards organized by APECS and SCAR</p>	<p>BEST OVERALL:</p> <p>Best Overall Early Career Oral Presentation: Theresa King (University of South Florida, United States) - Mid-20th century intrusion of Circumpolar Deep Water on Ross Sea and Wilkes Land continental margins evidenced by stylaster-coral isotopic signals.</p> <p>Best Overall Early Career Poster Presentation: Francyne Elias-Piera (Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil) - E-learning course on the Antarctic environment: An interdisciplinary and collaborative production</p> <p>ASIAN Region:</p> <p>1st Place Early Career Oral Presentation: Wee Cheah (Academia Sinica, Taiwan) - The role of mixing and silicate in regulating phytoplankton community structure in the iron-limited Antarctic Polar Front</p> <p>2nd Place Early Career Oral Presentation: Abiramy Krishnan (University of Malaya, Malaysia) - Influence of temperature on amylase and cellulase activity from polar and tropical soil microfungi</p> <p>Best Early Career Poster: Shridhar Jawak (National Centre for Antarctic and Ocean Research, India) - Empirical modelling of bathymetry of Antarctic lakes using high-resolution multispectral imagery</p> <p>AFRICAN & MIDDLE EAST Region:</p> <p>1st Place Early Career Oral Presentation: Jean Looek (Stellenbosch University, South Africa) - The seasonal distribution and controls of bioactive trace elements cadmium and cobalt in the southern ocean, Atlantic sector.</p> <p>2nd Place Early Career Oral Presentation: Trevor McIntyre (University of Pretoria, South Africa) - Long-term niche fidelity in southern elephant seals: Do individuals display unique foraging strategies?</p> <p>Best Early Career Poster: Ryan Cloete (Stellenbosch University, South Africa) - The distribution and controls of bioactive trace elements (Cu and Zn) in the Atlantic Sector of the Southern Ocean.</p> <p>AUSTRALASIAN & OCEANIA Region:</p> <p>1st Place Early Career Oral Presentation: Taryn Noble (Institute for Marine and Antarctic Studies, Australia) - Testing the ice-ocean feedback mechanism: Reliable extraction of proxy data from surface sediments on the East Antarctic margin.</p> <p>2nd Place Early Career Oral Presentation: Hanne Nielsen (University of Tasmania, Australia) - Hoofprints in Antarctica: The significance of Byrd's polar dairy.</p> <p>Best Early Career Poster: Diana King (University of Wollongong, Australia) - Semi-automated Antarctic vegetation monitoring using digital photography</p> <p>EUROPEAN & RUSSIAN Region:</p> <p>1st Place Early Career Oral Presentation: Muhammed Jeofry (Imperial College London, United Kingdom) - Geophysical investigations of the subglacial embayment in the Institute Ice Stream of West Antarctica</p>

2nd Place Early Career Oral Presentation: **George Roth** (Norwegian Polar Institute, Norway) - Quantarctica 3.0: A Cross-Platform, Full-Featured Open GIS for Antarctic Research

Best Early Career Poster: **Rachel Downey** (Senckenberg Natural History Museum and Research Institute, Germany) - Biogeographic review of carnivorous sponges in the Southern Ocean

NORTH AMERICAN Region:

1st Place Early Career Oral Presentation: **Cassandra Brooks** (Stanford University, United States) - Competing values and political complexity in the Southern Ocean: CCAMLR and the challenge of marine protected areas

2nd Place Early Career Oral Presentation: **Michelle Shero** (University of Alaska - Anchorage, United States) - Do Weddell seals "freeze" pregnancy? Intra-specific variation in gestation of a top Antarctic predator

Best Early Career Poster: **Jade Lawrence** (Louisiana State University, United States) - Subsurface hypersaline brine discharge from Taylor Glacier into Lake Bonney at depth

SOUTH AMERICAN Region:

1st Place Early Career Oral Presentation: **Camila Signori** (University of São Paulo, Brazil) - Assessing the impact of climate change on microbial diversity across environmental gradients in the southern ocean

2nd Place Early Career Oral Presentation: **Claudio Rivas** (Austral University of Chile, Chile) - Stress response in *Chlorella* sp. isolated from snow community in King George Island

Best Early Career Poster: **Patricia Saez** (University of Concepción, Chile) - Diffusive and biochemical limitations to photosynthesis in Antarctic plants from two populations in Antarctica

6. Outlook for 2016-2017

APECS will be celebrating its 10th anniversary throughout 2017! The upcoming term will be particularly special for us, and we want to celebrate it with all of our members and partners. Plans are already underway for many events and activities including the APECS International Polar Weeks and Antarctica Day 2016, workshops at the Arctic Frontiers 2017 conference in Tromsø Norway (January 2017), the [International Symposium on The Cryosphere in a Changing Climate](#) in Wellington, New Zealand (February 2017), the [Arctic Science Summit Week 2017](#) in Prague, Czech Republic (April 2017), the [9th International Congress of Arctic Social Sciences](#) in Umeå, Sweden (June 2017), the [Joint SCAR Humanities and Social Sciences and History Expert Group Conference](#) in Hobart, Australia (July 2017), and many more. The APECS International Online Conference will take place in March 2017 and we will award the APECS International Mentor Award 2017. In addition, several of the APECS National Committees are currently planning their own workshops and education and outreach activities for the next year. Keep an eye out on the APECS website for announcements about these and other upcoming activities!

The year 2017 will mean big changes for the [APECS International Directorate](#) with its move from Norway to Germany. Having a dedicated full-time coordinator for APECS has been one of the major factors contributing to the success of the organization over the last 10 years and has enabled APECS to grow into the large international network that it is today. APECS therefore wants to very much thank the current Directorate funders in Tromsø, Norway ([Research Council of Norway](#), [UiT The Arctic University of Norway](#) and the [Norwegian Polar Institute](#)) for their generous support from 2009 to 2016 in helping us shape the future of polar research and supporting early career researchers around the world! From February 2017, our APECS International Directorate will be located at and funded by the [Alfred Wegener Institute \(AWI\) Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research](#) in Potsdam, Germany for the next five years. APECS is very thankful for this opportunity and commitment by AWI and is looking forward to a fruitful collaboration in the coming years to continue our work.

2017 will also see efforts by APECS to implement some of the changes and goals identified in the [2016-2020 Strategic Plan](#). This will involve trying new communication strategies in order to better reach APECS members, support National Committees around the world, strengthening our collaborations with our partners and identify what resources APECS can provide to expand our reach as an organization.

We are well on track to have an exciting and active anniversary year! We hope to see you at one of our many in-person or online events throughout the year. Remember, there are many ways to participate and contribute to shaping the future of polar research.